

**STUDY OF JADID LITERATURE IN FOREIGN
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Folklore of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan,****E-mail: 777farhodkenja777@gamil.com****UDC 821.512.133.09'06-047.48****ORCID: 0009-0004-4332-8951****<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17719929>****ARTICLE INFO**Received: 23rd November 2025Accepted: 24th November 2025Online: 25th November 2025**KEYWORDS**

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ABSTRACT

The history of our homeland is witness to many events. The movement, which began to put an end to the submissiveness that had prevailed for many years, was subjected to thousands of slanders and accusations in its time. During the Tsarist Russian invasion, the Governor-General of Fergana, Mikhail Skobelev, said: "To destroy a nation, it is not necessary to destroy it; it is enough to destroy its culture, art, and language, and soon it will perish itself..." The conspiracy to illiterate the nation has not lost its trace and influence until recently. The burden of destroying the nation fell upon the intellectual class of our homeland. Prominent representatives of the Jadid movement wrote works calling for the awakening of the nation, organized theaters, and published articles in newspapers encouraging the pursuit of knowledge. They wrote textbooks for schools and also worked as teachers

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He has always supported the younger generation in acquiring secular knowledge. Our leader's calls to study and teach the scientific work and arduous life path of the Jadid movement are not without reason. The President emphasizes that the study of the Jadids' contribution to national statehood remains relevant. We all know that our Jadid ancestors, who came forward with the noble idea of "Unity in language, thought, and deed," believed that the main way to bring our peoples out of ignorance and backwardness, to save them from the swamp of heedlessness, is through knowledge and enlightenment, and through achieving secular progress. Moreover, they specifically noted that the Jadid movement has not only

educational but also political significance: From this point of view, it is of particular importance that the main topics of discussion at today's conference are the research and systematization of the progressive ideas and views of our progressive ancestors, the study of the role and influence of the Turkestan Jadids in the development of national statehood, the analysis of the legislative framework of the state structures created by them in the first quarter of the 20th century, a historical assessment of their activities aimed at building a secular, legal and democratic society, and issues related to the fact that this heritage will serve as a solid foundation for building a New Uzbekistan and the Third Renaissance.

In today's era of globalization, attention to the study of Jadid literature in foreign literary studies has increased. In particular, the liberation movements of dependent nations during the colonial period attracted the attention of foreign researchers. The author of such studies is Jeff Sahadeo. Jeff Sahadeo is a professor and researcher who frequently investigates topics such as the history of Central Asia, the Caucasus, Russia, Eastern Europe and Eurasia, empire, migration and diaspora. Currently, he conducts research in Central Asia and the Caucasus. The policies pursued by the colonial state in Central Asia and the works illuminating the situation of the local population received great attention. In particular, the policy of illiteracy or Russification of the nation is openly stated.

The scholar has undertaken several major works illuminating the situation in Central Asia. "Everyday Life in Central Asia: Past and Present." According to Jeff Sahadeo, the word "civilization," which the Russians began to use in colonized Tashkent, slightly changed its meaning and was closer to "culture," "progress," which is often used in Europe. Moreover, the Russians encountered such a vibrant social and economic situation in Turkestan that it completely contradicted their rigid and backward perceptions of Asia. According to Sahadeo, the countries of Central Asia were sinking into backwardness under the guise of development. In addition, the scholar's works "Central Asia" and "The Modern Uzbeks" reveal the tragic history of Central Asia and the Uzbek people. Sahadeo Jeff was particularly interested in Uzbeks and in Tashkent. As proof of this, we can cite his views in the work "Russian Colonial Society in Tashkent."

The voice of the Jadid movement did not leave the scholars of distant lands indifferent. Today, the inclusion of their works in foreign literature and their presentation to the general public is a process of great importance.

List of used literature:

- 1.Sahadeo, Jeff. 2007. Russian colonial society in Tashkent, 1865 – 1923. Bloomington: Indiana University Press.
- 2.<https://www.xabar.uz/uz/mualliflar/bobur-nabi/millatni-savodsizlantirish-fitnasi>
- 3.<https://kun.uz/36197360>
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